

EFFECT OF OSMOPRIMING ON SEEDLING ESTABLISHMENT OF DRY BED DIRECT SEEDED BORO RICE

K. Sarker, M.A. Samad, M.A. Kader, M.M. Hossain and N. Mohammad

Department of Agronomy
Bangladesh Agricultural University
Mymensingh-2200, Bangladesh

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted at the Seed Laboratory, Department of Agronomy, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh to study the effect of osmopriming on germination and growth of rice seedling cv. BRRI dhan28. There were nineteen osmopriming treatments in the experiment viz. priming with 1% KCl for 15 hours, 20 hours and 25 hours, priming with 2% KCl for 15 hours, 20 hours and 25 hours, priming with 3% KCl for 15 hours, 20 hours and 25 hours, priming with 1% ZnSO₄ for 15 hours, 20 hours and 25 hours, priming with 2% ZnSO₄ for 15 hours, 20 hours and 25 hours, priming with 3% ZnSO₄ for 15 hours, 20 hours and 25 hours and zero (0) hour priming (control). The experiment was laid out in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with four replications. Result revealed that priming with 2% ZnSO₄ for 25 hours gave the highest germination percentage (94%), vigor index (19.41%), shoot length (17 cm), shoot dry weight (0.09 g), root length (16.5 cm) and root dry weight (0.36 g). It also took the lowest time (5.695 days) for total germination (mean germination time). Non-primed seed took the highest time (9.025 days) for total germination (mean germination time).

Key words: Osmopriming, Rice, Seedling Establishment.

Introduction

Germination and seedling establishment are critical stages in the plant life cycle. In crop production, stand establishment determines plant density, uniformity and management options (Hussain *et al.*, 2006). In arid and semi-arid environments, the water needed for germination is available for only a short period, and consequently, successful crop establishment depends not only on the rapid and uniform germination of the seed, but also on the ability of the seed to germinate under low water availability (Bradford *et al.*, 1990). However, if the stress effect can be alleviated at the germination stage, chances for attaining a good crop with economic yield production would be high (Rauf and Ashraf, 2001). Strategies for improving the growth and development of crop species have been investigated for many years. Seed priming is a pre-sowing strategy for influencing seedling development by modulating pre-germination metabolic activity prior to emergence of the radicle and generally enhances germination rate and plant performance (Ruan *et al.*, 2002). During priming, seeds are partially hydrated so that pre-germinative metabolic activities proceed, while radicle protrusion is prevented, then are dried back to the original moisture level (Kalita *et al.*, 2002). Various prehydration or priming treatments have been employed to increase the speed and synchrony of seed germination (Haigh and Barlow, 1987). Common priming techniques include osmopriming (soaking seeds in osmotic solutions such as polyethylene glycol), halopriming (soaking seeds in salt solutions) and hydropriming (soaking seeds in water). Osmopriming contributes to significant improvement in seed germination and seedling growth in different plant species. Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) production depends on a number of factors. Quality seed is one of the important factors for the production of rice. A good seed within a variety gives good stand establishment in the soil, which in turn ensures a good harvest. Seed quality is a multiple concept

comprising several components (Thomson, 1979) like germination capacity, viability, vigor, moisture content and seed health etc. Quality seed ensures quality seedling. It is an important and obligatory input to maintain optimum growth and better grain yield for modern rice varieties (BRRI, 2006). Optimum crop stand establishment is the prerequisite for successful production. If the crops are given a good start at the beginning of life, they usually grow well, strong and healthy. Crops often fail to establish quickly and uniformly, leading to decreased yield, because of low plant population. Constraints to good establishment of crops includes lack of soil moisture, low or high temperature, soil salinity, weed competition, low seed germination quality, extreme disease pressure etc. Seedling that germinates faster and grows rapidly are able to produce sufficient deep root system before the seed bed dried out and harden and these seedlings have enough competitive ability against weed and seedling diseases. If seeds are soaked in different chemical solutions, germination happens more quickly, resulting in a healthier crop. Germination and seedling growth are appraised on the basis of important physiological and biochemical attributes mainly related to the rapidity of germination, vigorous seedling and reserve metabolism pattern. Priming treatments have been found to enhance the amylase activity which is positively correlated with the reserve mobilization and germination rate in rice (Lee and Kim, 2000; Basra *et al.*, 2005). Priming increases level of α -amylase activity was reported by Basra *et al.* (2005) in hardened rice seeds. At this situation seed priming can be a simple solution towards stand establishment (Harris *et al.*, 2002). Good seedling establishment is an important constrain to crop production in semi arid tropics (Itabari *et al.*, 1993; Harris *et al.*, 1999). Priming in the semi- arid tropics has been reported to increase emergence, more vigorous plants, better drought tolerance, earlier maturing, higher grain yield (Harris *et al.*, 1999, 2001, 2002). Osmopriming of seeds are being used in many parts of the world to reduce the germination time, to get synchronized germination, improve germination rate and better seedling establishment in many field crops like rice (Lee and Kim, 1999, 2000; Basra *et al.*, 2003, 2004; Farooq *et al.*, 2004), wheat, maize (Dell and Tritto 1990; Basra *et al.*, 2003). Osmopriming practically ensured rapid and uniform germination and it had high potential in improving field emergence and ensured early flowering and harvesting under stress condition, especially in dry areas. Keeping above in mind the study was conducted to investigate the effects of osmopriming on seed germination and seedling establishment of rice cv. BRRI dhan28.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out at the Seed Laboratory of the Department of Agronomy, Bangladesh Agricultural University (BAU), Mymensingh during the period from September to December 2011. Seeds were collected from the Agronomy Field Laboratory, Department of Agronomy, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh. Nineteen treatments were used for the experiment viz. priming with 1% KCl for 15 hours, 20 hours and 25 hours, priming with 2% KCl for 15 hours, 20 hours and 25 hours, priming with 3% KCl for 15 hours, 20 hours and 25 hours, priming with 1% ZnSO₄ for 15 hours, 20 hours and 25 hours, priming with 2% ZnSO₄ for 15 hours, 20 hours and 25 hours, priming with 3% ZnSO₄ for 15 hours, 20 hours and 25 hours and zero (0) hour priming (control). The experiment was laid out in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with four replications. Seeds were soaked in 1, 2 and 3% of KCl and ZnSO₄ at room temperature (27±3°C). Soaked seeds were dried at room temperature and were used in the further tests. For germination and other tests, plastic pots (22 cm diameter and 10 cm depth) were filled with 2 kg of soil which was collected from the Agronomy

Field Laboratory. Collected soil was sun dried and ground well and properly cleaned. The amount of water hold by the soil was calculated according to Piper (1950). One hundred seeds were sown in each of 76 pots. Field capacity of the soil was maintained by supplying tap water manually. The data on germination percentage, mean germination time, vigor index, shoot length, shoot dry weight, root length and root dry weight were recorded. The daily record of germinated seed was taken up to 15 days from setting up of the test. For each priming treatments, germination percentage was calculated using the recommended formula. The mean germination time was calculated following Godchild *et al.* (1971). Daily count on germination of seed was taken to calculate seedling vigor index using the formula given by Maguire (1962). Seedling shoot and root length was recorded at 15 days after sowing. The shoot and root length of the seedlings were dried in an electric oven maintaining 72^o C temperature for 48 hours. Dry weights of shoot and root were measured accordingly. The collected data were analyzed statistically following the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) technique and the significance of the mean differences were adjudged by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) (Gomez and Gomez, 1984) using a statistical computer package program MSTAT-C.

Results and Discussion

Germination

Germination of rice seedling was significantly affected due to the priming treatments (Table 1). The highest germination (94%) was obtained in seed primed with 2% ZnSO₄ for 25 hours whereas the lowest value of germination (66%) was found in non primed seed. This result is similar to that of Farooq *et al.* (2006a). The results of the present study clearly showed that more germination advantages of the rice seed could be achieved by priming with different chemical. The result of the present study is in agreement with that of Lee *et al.* (1998) and Basra *et al.* (2005).

Mean germination time

The priming treatments exerted significant effect on mean germination time (days) of rice seedlings for different chemical treatments (Table 1). Under all the treatments, the highest mean germination time was found with non primed seed. The lowest mean germination time for priming with 2% ZnSO₄ for 25 hours. The results revealed that priming enhanced rapid germination of seed compared with non primed seed. This significant enhancement in germination might have been caused due to enhance of the amylase activity that is positively correlated with the reserve mobilization and mean germination rate in rice (Lee and Kim, 2000). The results revealed that primed rice seed emerged faster and decreased the mean germination time. Similar results were also found by Harris *et al.* (2002) and Lee *et al.* (1998).

Vigor index

The vigor index of rice seedlings was affected significantly by priming with different chemical treatments (Table 1). The highest vigor index was found with the seed primed with 2% ZnSO₄ for 25 hours. On the other hand the lowest vigor index values were found with non primed seed. The results showed that vigor index increased in primed seeds. The increased vigor index might be related to reduction of imbibition lag time for priming treatment (Harris *et al.*, 2002). Priming also causes physiological and biochemical changes in seed during the seed treatments and metabolic activities increases α -amylase activity, thus indicating higher vigor index (Lee and Kim, 2000).

Table 1. Effect of osmopriming of seed on germination percentage, mean germination time and vigor index of rice seed cv. BRRI dhan28

Treatments	Growth Parameters		
	Germination (%)	Mean Germination Time(days)	Vigor Index (%)
1%KCl +15h	79.25 h	6.418 bc	14.08 i
2%KCl +15h	81.5 g	6.475 b	14.45 i
3%KCl +15h	85 f	6.44 bc	15.16 h
1%KCl+20h	81.25 g	6.395 bcd	14.61 i
2%KCl+20h	88 de	6.15 def	16.64 ef
3%KCl+20h	87.5 de	6.19 cdef	16.42 fg
1%KCl+25h	87 e	6.298 bcd	16.02 g
2%KCl+25h	89.75 c	6.193 cdef	17.01 de
3%KCl+25h	90.75 c	6.013 ef	17.8 c
1%ZnSO ₄ +15h	88.25 d	6.242 bcde	16.61 ef
2%ZnSO ₄ +15h	90.5 c	6.007 ef	17.76 c
3%ZnSO ₄ +15h	89.75 c	6.142 def	17.2 d
1%ZnSO ₄ +20h	90.75 c	6.012 ef	17.87 c
2%ZnSO ₄ +20h	92.5 b	5.983 ef	18.43 b
3%ZnSO ₄ +20h	92 b	5.988 ef	18.21 bc
1%ZnSO ₄ +25h	92 b	5.96 f	18.24 bc
2%ZnSO ₄ +25h	94 a	5.695 g	19.41 a
3%ZnSO ₄ +25h	92.75 b	5.938 f	18.59 b
Zero priming	66 i	9.025 a	7.632 j
Significance	**	**	**
LSD	1.014	0.509	0.232
CV (%)	0.82	2.19	2.6

** = Significant at 1% level, * = Significant at 5% level, CV= Co-efficient of Variation

Shoot length

Shoot length of rice seedling was affected significantly as a result of osmopriming treatments (Table 2). The highest shoot length was found with seed primed with 2% ZnSO₄ for 25 hours treatment. On the other hand, the lowest shoot length (10.93 cm) value was found with non- primed seed. The result of the present study clearly showed that osmopriming enhanced shoot length of rice for soil with moisture stress condition. The similar results were also found by Tongma *et al.* (2001) and Farooq *et al.* (2006a).

Shoot dry weight

Seed priming treatments influenced significantly the growth of shoots dry weight of rice seedlings (Table 2). The highest shoot dry weight of rice seedlings (0.09 g) was obtained in seed primed with 2% ZnSO₄ for 25 hours whereas the lowest value (0.03 g) was found with no primed seed followed by 1% KCl for 15 hours and 1% KCl for 20 hours. The result is in agreement with that of Farooq *et al.* (2006a and 2008) and Tongma *et al.* (2001). Seed priming increased seedlings dry weight probably by enhancing K⁺ concentration in both seeds and seedlings, leading to improved α -amylase activity and the concentration of reducing sugars with amylase activity (Farooq *et al.*, 2007).

Root length

The root length was affected significantly due to the priming treatments (Table 2). The highest growth of root length (17 cm) was obtained in seed primed with 2% ZnSO₄ for 25 hours whereas the lowest value of growth of root length (7 cm) was found in 1% KCl for 15 hours.

Root dry weight

The root dry weight of rice seedling was affected significantly due to priming treatments (Table 2). The highest value (0.36 g) was found priming with 2% ZnSO₄ for 25 hours where the lowest value 0.04 g for non primed seed. The results of the present study clearly showed that root dry weight of rice seedling increased by priming.

Table 2. Effect of osmopriming of seed on shoot length (cm), shoot dry weight (g), root length (cm), root dry weight (g) of rice seedlings

Treatments	Growth Parameters			
	Shoot Length (cm)	Shoot Weight (g)	Root Length (cm)	Root Weight (g)
1%KCl +15h	7 h	0.035 f	6.5 i	0.0325 b
2%KCl +15h	8 gh	0.045 def	7.75 h	0.0375 b
3%KCl +15h	9 g	0.045 def	8.25 h	0.04 b
1%KCl+20h	8 gh	0.0375 f	8 h	0.04 b
2%KCl+20h	12 ef	0.0575 bcdef	11.5 ef	0.0575 b
3%KCl+20h	11 f	0.055 cdef	10.5 g	0.0525 b
1%KCl+25h	11 f	0.0575 bcdef	10.5 fg	0.0475 b
2%KCl+25h	10.75 f	0.065 bcde	12 e	0.0575 b
3%KCl+25h	14 cd	0.07 abc	13.75 cd	0.0625 b
1%ZnSo ₄ +15h	12 ef	0.055 cdef	11.5 ef	0.055 b
2%ZnSo ₄ +15h	14 cd	0.0675 abcd	13.25 d	0.0625 b
3%ZnSo ₄ +15h	13 de	0.065 bcde	12.25 e	0.06 b
1%ZnSo ₄ +20h	14 cd	0.0675 abcd	13.5 d	0.0675 b
2%ZnSo ₄ +20h	16 ab	0.075 abc	15 b	0.0675 b
3%ZnSo ₄ +20h	15 bc	0.0725 abc	14.75 bc	0.075 b
1%ZnSo ₄ +25h	15 bc	0.0725 abc	14.25 bcd	0.07 b
2%ZnSo ₄ +25h	17 a	0.09 a	16.5 a	0.36 a
3%ZnSo ₄ +25h	16 ab	0.08 ab	14.75 bc	0.07 b
Zero priming	8.75 g	0.0425 ef	8.25 h	0.035 b
Significance	**	**	**	**
LSD	1.534	0.02005	0.9393	0.1268
CV (%)	8.88	7.10	5.65	124.36

** = Significant at 1% level, * = Significant at 5% level, CV= Co-efficient of Variation

Conclusion

In rainfed areas, germination and subsequent seedling growth can be inhibited by adverse conditions in the field. Priming is helpful in reducing the risk of poor stand establishment under a wide range of environmental conditions. Our findings revealed osmopriming is a useful technique for enhancing seedling emergence rate of rice cv. BRRI dhan28. From the present study, it may be concluded that seed priming can enhance the seedling establishment of rice associated with all other parameters studied. Osmopriming with ZnSO₄ were the most promising priming techniques. Osmopriming of rice seeds with 2% ZnSO₄ for 25 hours enhance faster germination and vigorous growth of rice seedlings. These effects can improve seedling establishment and field performance of BRRI dhan28.

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